

Juvenile Delinquency of Senior High School Students in Surabaya, Indonesia

Herdina Indrijati

Abstract—This research aims to describe teenager delinquency behavior (Juvenile Delinquency) of senior high school students in Surabaya, Indonesia. Juvenile Delinquency is a broad range of behaviors start from socially unacceptable behavior (overreact in school), violation (escape from home) to crimes (like stealing). This research uses quantitative descriptive method using 498 students who come from 8 different schools in Surabaya as subjects. Juvenile Delinquency behavior form questionnaire has been completed by subjects and was used to measure and describe the behavior. The result of this research is presented in statistic descriptive forms. Result shows that 169 subjects skip school, 55 subjects get out of home without parent's permission, 110 subjects engage in smoking behavior, 74 subjects damage other people properties, 32 subjects steal, 16 subjects exploit others and 7 subjects engage in drug abuse. Frequency of the top five mentioned behavior are 1-10 times. It is also found that subject's peers are most likely to be the victim of Juvenile Delinquency. The reasons teenagers engage in Juvenile Delinquency include (1) feeling tired, bored or lazy – that contributes to their skip school behavior (2) Having a lot of problem with parents - contrives them to run away from home, (3) accidentally damage other people's properties, (4) financial problems – force them to steal and exploit, (5) feeling like having a lot of life problems – that makes them do drugs (6) trying smoking for experience.

Keyword—Juvenile delinquency, senior high school, student.

I. INTRODUCTION

A lot of changes happen in human physical and psychological ability during the adolescent phase, which makes adolescent phase to some people is memorized as a beautiful phase in life. Adolescent is described as a developmental transition phase between childhood and adulthood, that includes biological, cognitive, and socio-emotional changes [5]. The rapid developmental changes in adolescent phase makes an individual improve in many social aspects of life, such as broader social relation, development of self-identity, decision making, planning future career, talent development, etc. Positive adolescent development is expected by everyone, but there are always chances for some problems and distraction to show up during the developmental process.

Any socially unacceptable behavior (religion, norms, ethics, school & family rules, etc.) is called deviation and if the deviation behavior breaks the law, it is called Juvenile Delinquency [6]. Juvenile Delinquency consists of two categories that can be used to distinguish deviate behaviors in adolescent [5], (a) *index offenses*, refer to crime committed by teenagers or adult, such as robbery, murder, violence and rape and (b) *status offenses*, refer to less serious cases that does not

break the law – that are mostly committed by teenagers (juvenile offences). Some examples of the offences are escaping from home, skipping school, drinking alcohol, prostitution, and vandalism.

Juvenile Delinquency has been increasing significantly in recent couple of years. More varied cases are displayed on television and written media. Data from *Markas Besar Kepolisian Republik Indonesia* (Indonesian National Police Headquarters) reported by Indonesia Central Bureau of Statistics show that during 2007 about 3.100 people that had been identified as criminals are 18 years old or below [2]. The number of Juvenile Delinquency kept on increasing. In 2008 and 2009, it was reported that 3.300 adolescent and 4.200 adolescent committed Juvenile Delinquency behavior. The data presented by *Komisi Nasional Perlindungan Anak (Komnas PA)* or national commission of child protection, shows that crimes committed by adolescent and children increased 35% higher from January to October 2009 compared to the previous years [3]. In Surabaya region, the highest juvenile crime takes place in Kenjeran District. The police officer in Kenjeran has announced that since March to August 2009, there are 23 cases of stealing and other crimes that are committed by children. The youngest criminal is 13 years old and the oldest is 17 years old [1].

The increases of juvenile crime are growing some concern. Since most of the data are based on research that was conducted 6 to 10 years ago – thus researcher wants to get a more updated data of Juvenile Delinquency. Researcher wants to describe Juvenile Delinquency of senior high school students in Surabaya, Indonesia.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Procedure and Research Subject

TABLE I
RESEARCH SUBJECT BASED ON HOME SCHOOL

School Type	Amount	Percentage
1 State Senior High	60	12,04%
4 Private Senior High	245	49,19%
2 State Vocational Senior High	133	26,7%
1 Private Vocational Senior High	60	12,04%
Totals	498	

There are 498 subjects participating in this research, consisting of students from early adolescent and middle adolescent. Subjects come from 1 state senior high school, 4 private schools, 2 state vocational high school, 1 private vocational high school in Surabaya. Subjects have been asked

Herdina Indrijati is with the Faculty of Psychology Universitas Airlangga (e-mail: herdina.indrijati@psikologi.unair.ac.id).

to participate by completing the form of Juvenile Delinquency Questionnaire.

B. Research Instrument

The questionnaire used in this research was constructed by the researcher aiming to identify forms of Juvenile Delinquency. Descriptive data identified in this research include:

1. Juvenile Delinquency behavior includes: (a) skipping school, (b) getting out of home without parent's permission, (c) smoking, (d) damaging other people's properties without any responsibility (e) taking money or properties that belongs to someone else (stealing), (f) rudely forcing to take or ask other people properties or money (exploitation), (g) use drugs
2. Frequency of Juvenile Delinquency behavior
3. Victim of Juvenile Delinquency
4. Location of Juvenile Delinquency
5. Reason behind Juvenile Delinquency

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Research Result

Result description of Juvenile Delinquency is presented in Tables II-IVX.

TABLE II
SUBJECT BASED ON AGE

Age	Amount	Percentage
14 years old	21	2.81
15 years old	139	27.91
16 years old	183	36.74
17 years old	143	28.71
18 years old	10	2.008
Blank	2	
Totals	498	

TABLE III
SUBJECT BASED ON SEX

Sex	Amount	Percentage
Boys	228	37
Girls	265	63
Blank	5	
Totals	498	

TABLE IV
JUVENILE DELINQUENCY FORM

	Skipping School	Get Out Without Parent's Permission	Smoking	Damage Other People Properties	Stealing	Exploiting	Drug Abuse
Yes	169	55	110	74	32	16	7
No	329	442	398	424	466	482	491

TABLE V
FREQUENCY OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY

	Skipping School	Get Out without Parent's Permission	Damage Other People Properties	Stealing	Exploiting
Seldom	17	1	3	4	-
Always	18	5	1	2	2
1-10 times	64	30	39	22	12
10-15 times	14	2	-	-	-
Clueless	19	-	-	-	-
Infinite	8	1	4	-	-
Blank	14	7	-	-	-
Sometimes	5	-	3	1	-
Forget	8	9	24	3	2
20-50	2	-	-	-	-

TABLE VI
LOCATION OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY

	Skipping School	Moving Out without Parent's Permission
Canteen	86	-
House	15	-
Stall/café	12	3
Friend's house	12	24
Around the School	8	-
Internet Kiosk	6	2
Blank	13	2
Mall	5	2
Musholla (prayers place)	2	-
Toilet	2	-
Streets	9	13
Cousin's House	-	8
Sport Places	-	1

TABLE VII
VICTIM OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY

	Stealing	Exploiting	Vandalism
Friends	15	13	43
Family	8	1	7
Forget	5		17
Substantial	2		
Seniors	1	1	1
Strangers	1		5
Juniors		1	
Neighbor			1

TABLE VIII
7 REASON OF SKIPPING SCHOOL DURING SCHOOL TIME

Reason	Amount	Percentage
Tired / lazy / bored	59	34.91
Hungry and thirsty during class	33	19.53
Not comfortable with the teacher	27	15.98
Refreshing	10	5.92
Not comfortable with the subject	7	4.14
Late	6	3.55
Invited by friend	5	2.96
Others	22	

TABLE IX
7 REASON FOR MOVING OUT WITHOUT PARENT'S PERMISSION

Reason	Amount	Percentage
Parents Issues	22	40
Bored while at home	8	14.55
Angry and afraid to ask for permission	6	10.91
Blank	5	9.09
Disturbed	5	9.03
Hangout with friends	3	5.45
Fighting Parents	2	3.64
Others	4	7.28

TABLE X
7 REASON TO DAMAGE OTHER PEOPLE'S PROPERTIES WITHOUT RESPONSIBILITY

Reason	Amount	Percentage
Not Respond	25	33.78
Accidently	24	32.43
Unstable Emotion	6	8.11
Afraid of Compensation	6	8.11
Hate	5	6.76
Recessive	2	2.70
Accident	1	1.35
Others	3	4.05

TABLE XI
7 REASON TO TAKE OTHER PEOPLE MONEY OR PROPERTIES WITHOUT OWNER PERMISSION (STEALING)

Reason	Amount	Percentage
Financial Need	12	37.5
Not Respond	6	18.75
Recessive	4	12.5
Want to Have	4	12.5
Random	2	6.25
Blank Mind	2	6.25
Lost Property	1	3.13
Others	1	3.13

TABLE XII
7 REASON TO TAKE MONEY OR PROPERTIES THAT BELONG TO OTHER PEOPLE WITH FORCE (EXPLOIT)

Reason	Amount	Percentage
Not Respond	3	18.75
No Money	3	18.75
Recessive	2	12.5
Jealousy	2	12.5
Joke	2	12.5
Need	2	12.5
Others	2	12.5

TABLE XIII
REASON BEHIND USING DRUGS

Reason	Amount	Percentage
Currently in the Middle of Many Problem	3	42,85
Calm	1	14,28
Part of Life	1	14,28
Stress / Depression	1	14,28

TABLE XIV
7 REASON BEHIND SMOKING

Reason	Amount	Percentage
Following Friends	24	21.8
Want to Try	38	34,5
Stress Reliever	8	7,2
Smoking Addiction	7	6,3
Eliminate Boredom	4	3,6
Social Effect	4	3,6
Release Worry	3	2,7
Others	23	

B. Discussion

Result describes forms of Juvenile Delinquency behavior of research sample. If we take a look on Table II, it shows that the participant's ages, range of 14-18 years old. Table III shows sex type - there are more number of girls who participate in this research than boys. Table IV shows common forms of Juvenile Delinquency behavior, from higher to lower are skipping schools, smoking behavior, followed by damaging other people properties without responsibility.

In Table V, the highest frequency of Juvenile Delinquency is skipping school. 64 subjects mention that they have been skipping school for 1-10 times, 18 subjects admit to often skip school and 14 subjects skip school for 10-15 times. 30 students admit they get out of home without parent's permission about 1-10 times, and 5 students admit they frequently commit in the behavior. The data of damaging other people's properties show that 39 subjects admit they do it for 1-10 times, and 4 subjects do it in an infinite frequency. The data of stealing behavior show that 22 students say that they have committed stealing for 1-10 times, and 2 students admit they have done it in substantial amount. Rudely forcing someone to give their properties (exploiting behavior) data show that 12 people have done it for 1-10 times and 2 people admit they often do it.

In Table VI, canteen is chosen by 86 subjects as the destination for skipping school followed by home which is chosen by 15 subjects. Some other places that are chosen as the destination for skipping school are café, friend's house, street, around the school, mall, *musholla* (prayers house), etc. Destination that is chosen to get out of home without parent's permission are friend's house - that is chosen by 24 subjects, followed by café, streets, and cousin's house.

Table VII shows the victim of juvenile such as victim of robbery, exploitation, and vandalism. It is shown that subject's peer and family are most likely to be the victim of mentioned offences.

The reason subjects committed Juvenile Delinquency varied according to the specific behavior that is done, as shown in Tables VIII-XIV. The top chosen reasons for skipping school

are feeling tired, lazy, bored, hungry or thirsty during class period, and feeling uncomfortable towards the teacher. The most chosen reason why subjects get out of home without parent's permission are having issues with parents, boredom and anger. Subjects that committed vandalism said that they did it accidentally, and were afraid to indemnify the owners. The reasons for stealing behavior are financial need, recessive and the urge to buy something. For the exploitation behavior, the highest chosen reasons are cashless, recessive, and jealousy. For drug abuse, 3 people mentioned that their reasons are having problems, and the rest admit doing it to calm themselves from stress. For smoking behavior, reasons include peer pressure, smoking for experience, relieving stress, addicted, etc.

Sex type affects juvenile delinquency, whereas boys are more likely to engage in juvenile delinquency than girls. Specifically, boys are more likely to be antisocial and committed crimes while girls are more likely to escape from home [5]. Although, this research does not specifically measure the distribution of sex type in each juvenile delinquency, it identifies juvenile delinquency in general.

Subjects' ages range between 14 and 18 years, which can be categorized as early and middle adolescent phase. There are certain crises in middle adolescent phase that are characterized by heightened sensitivity and experience of persistent negative and labile mood states [4]. The accelerated development condition in adolescent phase causes changes in social development. They often form groups with same-aged friends, do a lot of activity together in groups, which can be both positive and aggressive such as stealing persecution, etc.

The forms of juvenile delinquency that are committed by subjects of this research are delinquency that causes material harm (vandalism, stealing, exploitation), social harm (drug abuse), and delinquency against status (skipping school, escaping home) [6]. Juvenile delinquency is divided into four types [6]. The first type is delinquency that causes a physical harm to others (rape, robbery, murder). The second type is delinquency that causes material harm (vandalism, stealing, pickpocketing, extortion). The third type is delinquency that causes social harm (prostitution, drug abuse, sex before marriage (base on Indonesian's norms). The fourth is delinquency against status (skipping school, escaping home, rebelling). Subjects in this research are a senior high school students in Surabaya. Subjects participate in this research committed three out of four delinquency types mentioned above. The delinquency types from higher to lower rate of frequency are skipping school, escaping home, followed by vandalism and stealing.

If we look to the frequency of delinquency behavior of students, behavior with the highest rate is delinquency against status, such as skipping school and get out of home without parent's permission. Meanwhile, delinquency that causes material harm (vandalism, stealing, exploitation) is on the second place.

Juvenile delinquency is divided into two categories according to [5]: (a) Index offense is a violent crime (robbery, rape, murder). (b) Status offence is a violation of the law only

because of the youth's status as a minor (typically anyone under 18 years old). Common examples of status offenses include skipping school and escaping home. If we look at the distribution of juvenile delinquency, subjects of this research have committed some index offenses such as stealing, extortion, damage other people's properties and status offenses including escaping from home, truant, and drug abuse. It can be summarized that subjects that participate in this research are more likely to do status offense than index offense.

As mentioned earlier about adolescent social development, they often form groups with same-aged friends. It seems like subjects are also make their friends as their juvenile delinquency victims. Their friends become top target for stealing, exploitation, and vandalism offences.

The most chosen reason behind subject's truant behavior is uncomfortable feeling about their school's condition. Uncomfortable feeling is caused by feeling bored, tired or lazy, and dislike towards the teacher. This condition can be understood when the lessons given in class is considered as useless by students. The situation can lead to social conflict situation, as it triggers students to dislike towards their teacher, and to gather against them [4].

Subject's motivation to get out of home without parent's permission seems to be dominated by the issues with parents (fighting with parents, bored at home, scolded, parent's fight). Dispute, inconsistency, and not suitable family discipline could also be the main causes of juvenile delinquency [5].

Result shows that drug abuse cases do not show any significant result. Even though there are only small number of subjects who committed the behavior (7 people), this must be seen as a serious warning. It indicates that some of Surabaya students have been involved in drug abuse. They mention the reasons behind the behavior are having problems and use drugs to calm themselves. Some adolescents explain that releasing stress is one of the reason why they use drugs, from which indicates limited coping skills, and irresponsible decision making [5]. Drug abuse in adolescent will have long term impact which could distract the development of responsible and competent behavior.

Smoking behavior in Surabaya's senior high school student shows some serious concern because 110 out of 498 say that they engage in smoking behavior. They mentioned that peer and social influences are the main reason they engage in the behavior. Peer gives impact to juvenile delinquency behavior as interacting with negative influence strengthens the likelihood to become negative as well [5]. Besides, trying for experience occupies the highest rating. This condition is seen as one of the characteristic of adolescent development - the urge to try something new and do some experiment.

REFERENCES

- [1] *6 Bulan Angka Kriminal Anak dibawah Umur Tinggi*. Accessed on 20 April 2012. Retrieved from <http://surabaya.detik.com/read/2009/09/01/091523/1193666/466/6-bulan-angka-kriminal-anak-dibawah-umur-tinggi>
- [2] Badan Pusat Statistik (2010) *Profil Kriminalitas Remaja*. Accessed on 26 October 2016. Retrieved from

https://www.bps.go.id/website/pdf_publicasi/profil-kriminalitas-remaja-2010

- [3] *Jumlah Anak dan Remaja Pelaku Kriminal Meningkat*. Accessed on 11 April 2012. Retrieved from <http://www.nusantaraku.org/forum/archive/index.php/t-16476.htm>
- [4] Monk, F.J., Knoers, A.M.P., Haditono, Siti Rahayu (2002). *Psikologi Perkembangan: Pengantar Dalam Berbagai Bagiannya*. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press
- [5] Santrock, J. W. (2002). *Life Span Development: Perkembangan Masa Hidup. Terjemahan*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [6] Sarwono, S., Meinarno, E. (2010). *Psikologi Remaja*. Jakarta: Salemba Humanika.